

ISSN: 2456-5474

RNI No. UPBIL/2016/68367

VOL.- X , ISSUE- V June - 2025
Innovation The Research Concept

A Study on the CRM Practices of Selected Retail Stores in Rajasthan

Paper Id : 20240 Submission Date : 2025-06-12 Acceptance Date : 2025-06-21 Publication Date : 2025-06-25
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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.16872471

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Abstract

Customer relationship management has been defined as a business philosophy focusing on mainly two-fold objectives of customer acquisition and retention. Amidst stiff competition, CRM can play a differentiating move for retailers to create value for both customers and the organization. The present paper studies the practices, programmes and procedures adopted by selected retail units of Rajasthan. A semi- structured questionnaire and interview method is employed to understand the CRM practices of Big Bazaar, Reliance Smart and Vishal Mega Mart. The paper presents the CRM practices adopted by these retail stores and emphasize that effective CRM practices can enhance value for both customer and company.

Keywords Customer Relationship Management, Retail, Practices.

Introduction

Business and society moves hand in hand. Success of any business depends on the response of the community to which it serves. At the same time existence of any business rests on sustaining the value that it generates. Creating and maintaining such value requires a coordinated strategic approach. The unprecedented change in technology had offered countless options in the hands of consumers. They are not only well connected with the world but also more informed. The differentiation once crafted by one company no longer stays unique. It is easily replicated by existing and new competitors and customer fidelity gets eroded. Furthermore, changing lifestyle and demographic composition also demands marketers to respond differently to the changing times. Increased participation of women in the workforce, dominance of nuclear families and growing number of elderly people indicate the desire of consumers to be served individually with their own unique requirements. Therefore the power has shifted from retailers to consumers which require marketers to recognize the dynamic forces and append their business strategies with new forms of differentiation which can be enhanced. Hence, customer relationship management acts as a customer focused philosophy which involves total commitment on the part of the entire organisation and improves service performance.

Objective of study

The purpose of research is to systematically uncover the answers to the problems and draw useful conclusions. Keeping this underlying principle of research the present study aims to study the customer relationship practices adopted by selected retailers.

Review of Literature

Parvatiyar & Sheth (2001) explored the conceptual foundations of CRM and concluded that the domain extends to wide areas of marketing and strategic decisions. CRM emerges as a principal exemplar of marketing when cooperation and collaboration with customers is imbedded into marketing practice and research. Also CRM should not be considered.

Ryals & Knox (2001) explored the issues that support or obstruct the development of CRM in the service sector; the organizational issues of culture and communication, management metrics and cross functional integration. The conclusions stated that marketing actions must focus on long-term customer relationships. This requires changes in business measurements and incentives and change in working practices for achieving the appropriate results.

Bull (2003) explained various aspects of CRM and highlighted that CRM is an intricate and a holistic approach which requires proper integrated systems. The study also discussed the importance of effective leadership, sourcing and evaluation within CRM strategies.

Chen, &Popovich (2003) explained that as a comprehensive approach CRM promises to maximize relationships with all customers, distribution channel members, and suppliers. Getting to "know" each customer through data mining techniques and a customer-centric business strategy helps the organization to proactively and consistently offer (and sell) more products and services for improved customer retention and loyalty over longer periods of time. They also elaborated how CRM technology application can manage globally dispersed customers by linking customer touch points to back office and front office functions.

Scullin, Fjermestad & Romano Jr (2004) in their work reflected that companies have been successful by embracing eCRM. Through proper execution of eCRM companies can identify the needs of customers which help in implementing new products, launching new marketing campaigns and satisfying customer needs and wants.

Wang, Lo, Chi & Yang (2004) developed a framework of customer value and CRM performance on the basis of key dimensions of customer value and explored the effect of customer value on CRM performance in terms of relationship quality and customer behavior. The study was conducted with two securities firms and their equal numbers of customers in China. The study concluded that there should be a balance among different measures of customer relationship performance. Customer behaviour-based CRM performance can be improved by building strong brand loyalty and customer satisfaction.

Boulding, Staelin, Ehret, & Johnston (2005) asserted that CRM is the outcome of the continuing evolution and integration of marketing ideas and newly available data, technologies, and organizational forms and predicted that CRM will not discontinue, rather it will keep evolving with the continuous amalgamation of ideas and technologies into the activities of CRM.

Javalgi, Martin & Young (2006) cited various anecdotes and case examples to present the interrelationship between market research, market orientation and customer relationship management issues. They asserted that unifying and integrating market research information with market orientation concepts positively influence components of customer relationship marketing.

Nguyen, Sherif & Newby (2007) suggested strategies for successful implementation of CRM. Organizations should coordinate CRM with business strategies for its proper implementation. Effective CRM programs can help companies in creating competitive advantage.

Tamošiūniene & Jasilioniene (2007) described CRM as business strategy and analyzed its origins, development and changes. Instead of considering CRM a software choice, the study suggested that it should be rather viewed as a strategy as it has impacts on the whole enterprise. Successful CRM requires strong leadership and governance, measurement parameters, close -knitted technology and a process based approach of viewing the problem.

Mishra & Mishra (2009) affirmed that customer centric organizations must adopt CRM as a core business strategy for delivering superior performance. Since organizations face challenges in implementation of CRM the authors suggested that CRM must be aligned with the business strategy of not selling the products but offering solutions.

Keramati, Mehrabi & Mojir (2010) in their study intended a process-oriented framework for examining the relationship among CRM resources, CRM process capabilities, and organizational performance by collecting data from 77 Iranian Internet service providers. The results indicated that infrastructural CRM resources affect CRM processes more than the technological CRM resources. The authors also suggested that the findings of the study can be applied to other industries because CRM benefits do not vary greatly across industries.

Rababah, Mohd, & Ibrahim (2011) did extensive literature review related to CRM processes. The review focused on different perspectives, the various types and the levels of CRM processes. The paper explained four major perspectives of CRM processes which are customer facing level processes, customer oriented processes, cross functional CRM processes and CRM macro-level processes. Among these processes, the authors highlighted that cross functional CRM process perspective is the most pervasive perspective of CRM as it explain not only list of mere processes but also it explains the nature of each process, the main activities within each process, and how each process interact with one another. They advocated that organisations should understand the different levels of CRM process and the integrated activities among the CRM process at each level for successful adoption and implementation of CRM. Their paper suggested a pre-implementation plan for CRM programs/systems which aims to initiate and communicate a customer-oriented culture within the organization.

Zamil (2011) described that there is a strong relationship between HR and use of CRM strategy to measure performance in order to enhance customer satisfaction. For achieving objectives of the business CRM should be linked with the mission of the organization for building profitable customer relationships.

Awasthi (2012) portrayed the impact of Customer Relationship Management practices in increasing the Sales Volume for organized retail stores located in Indore City. The results of the study explained that Practicing CRM, have gained over there sales volume from those organizations not practicing CRM.

Padmavathy, Balaji, & Sivakumar (2012) developed a multi-item scale for measuring the customer relationship management effectiveness (CRME) in Indian retail banks and to examine its relationship with key customer response variable. Two different studies were adopted to develop and validate the scale for CRME. The first study was conducted to identify key dimensions of CRMR by collecting responses from 197 Indian retail banking customers. In the second study, nomological validity for CRME scale was done by using a new sample of 261 actual bank customers. The study also examined relationship between dimensions of CRME and customer behaviour outcomes such as customer satisfaction, loyalty and cross-buying. Five dimensions for CRME were identified using factor analysis namely organizational commitment, customer experience, process-driven approach, reliability and technology-orientation. Out of these five dimensions, organizational commitment, process-driven approach and reliability were found to positively affect customer satisfaction. Reliability was found to have direct association with customer loyalty and both customer satisfaction and loyalty-influenced cross-buying.

Demo & Rozzett (2013) developed and validated Customer Relationship Management Scale by conducting three studies with different samples in America. The results found out that American customers give relevance to their relationship with companies which also influence shopping experience, satisfaction and loyalty. The CRMS was validated and included 14 items.

Dumitrescu, Tichindelean, & Vinerean (2013) presented application of the factor analysis in the realm of relationship marketing. Literature review was done to comprehend the concept of customer loyalty which is an important variable of relationship marketing. Data was collected from 215 customers of petrol-stations within the area of Sibiu City, Romania. Loyalty is defined by its two dimensions behavioral and attitudinal. The objective of the present study focused on attitudinal dimension of loyalty. The attitudinal dimension is understood through the three components of the human psyche: affective, cognitive and conative. The study found two factors which can measure the conative dimension of loyalty that are intention to rebuy the company's offer if the decision making conditions remain unchanged and intention to rebuy the company's offer when the price increases with 5%.

Dutot (2013) did an exploratory research on social customer relationship management (SCRM) strategy. The study was conducted with 40 French firms for identifying customer's perception of SCRM. Results showed that most of the top companies are not considering SCRM to the degree desired by customers.

Korneta (2014) examined Net Promoter Score Index introduced by Reichheld (2003) based on customers willingness to recommend a company to a friend. The data was collected from retail customers through survey and statistical analysis was presented. The survey was conducted with 2568 Polish customer who were asked a set of questions about 50 Polish retailers. The study concluded that retailers should focus on building relationship with customers and willingness of customers to recommend a company is a good indicator of strong business performance and a predictor of business growth. NPS index was found to be highly correlated with Trust. The research also indicated high correlation between NPS and other criteria like Value for money, products that are suited

to me or wide choice of products. The study also highlighted that low prices are less influential factor and it can be said that customers consider it a complete separate factor.

Fozia, Shiamwama, &Otiso (2014) assessed the impact of customer relationship management on a company's sales performance and gaining competitive advantage. The study concluded that CRM leads to long term sustainable profitability, increases customer confidence, improves the way customers view the company, increases repeat purchase etc.

Balamurgan & Kumar (2016) tried to investigate the elements of CRM to review the effective relationship between CRM, customer fulfillment and customer trust of the selected organization. Four critical elements namely interaction management, relationship development, customer service and employees' behavior were identified based on previous studies.

Upadhyaya (2016) is of the view that CRM is an adoptive marketing strategy. it is an extension to the customer focused marketing. However success of CRM programs depend on effective implementation an all the aspects.

Methodology

Research methodology is a framework of tools and techniques that enables in conducting research. It seeks to provide the framework for making original contribution by making advancement in the existing trove of knowledge repository.

Research Design

Research design is a blue print for conducting research. A well thought research design is objective based structure or framework. This research design for the present study is descriptive in nature.

Time Dimension

The present research employs cross - sectional study in which the researcher studies for aspects during a certain time period. Phenomena are not studied over the years.

Locale of the Study

This study is confined to the organized retail stores of three major cities in Rajasthan viz. Jaipur, Ajmer and Udaipur.

Selection of the Sample

The sampling design in the present study is based on non-probability sampling. Some of the methods in non-probability sampling are judgmental sampling and convenience sampling. In the present study, selection of the respondent organization is done on the basis of Judgmental Sampling Technique. The selected retail stores are Big Bazaar, Reliance Smart and Vishal Mega Mart. For accomplishing the research objectives, responses were sought from 8 store managers

Selection of Research Tool

The study was based on a descriptive research design. Interview combined with questionnaire technique was used for the investigation.

Data Collection

There are two sources of data for research, namely primary and secondary data. Data collected by the researcher for the first time for the study is known as primary data. Tools used for collecting primary data are questionnaire, schedules, observation, etc. Semi structured interview and questionnaire was used to seek response from store managers. Secondary data refers to the studies already conducted. Published articles, newsletters, reports, organization's database, government surveys etc. were looked into for gathering relevant information.

Tools Used The study was based on a descriptive research design. Interview combined with questionnaire technique was used for the investigation.

Analysis

Practices in relation to maintaining proper database of customers and employing methodology for segmentation.

Table1: Response of retailers with respect to maintaining computerized database

Response	N	%
Yes	7	87.50
No	1	12.50
Total	8	100.00

Most of the retailers (87.5%) maintain computerized data of customers.

Table2: Response of retailers with respect to segmentation of customers

Response	N	%
Yes	4	50.00
No	3	37.50
No Response	1	12.50
Total	8	100.00

Most of the retailers (50%) segment the customers to identify and fulfill the needs of particular customer segment. However some retailers (37.5%) responded that they don't segment the market. There was no response from one retailer.

Practices with respect to customer defection

Table3: Response of retailers for having policy for identifying customer defection

Response	N	%
Yes	7	87.50
No	1	12.50
Total	8	100.00

Almost all the retailers (87.5%) have facilities to identify customer defection.

Table 4: Response of retailers towards the policies for retaining lost customers

Response	N	%
Analyze the transactions with the customer and locating gaps in service delivery or unattended complaints	5	62.50
Interview with sales person responsible for customer interaction	3	37.50
One-to-one interview with lost customers	1	12.50

Policy for retaining old customers is as important as acquisition of customers. Most of the retailers (62.5%) have policy of analyzing the transactions with the customer and locating gaps in service delivery or unattended complaints. Some retailers (37.5%) also interview sales person responsible for customer interaction. However, one-to-one interview with lost customers is done by only one retailer.

Practices and efforts for maintaining relationship with existing customers

Table 5: Preference of retailers with respect to different measures adopted for Customer acquisition and informing existing customers

Action	N	%	Rank
1. Advertisement in local newspapers	7	87.50	1
2. Information about new arrivals is provided through e-mail	7	87.50	1
3. Mobile (SMS)	7	87.50	1
4. Pamphlets are printed	6	75.00	2
5. Call centers/ Toll free help lines	6	75.00	2
6. Wall Ads/ Billboards/ Hoardings	6	75.00	2
7. E-mail response	5	62.50	3
8. Information is provided on company's web site (facility for brochure downloads)	5	62.50	3
9. Product demonstration in colonies	4	50.00	4
10. Information is provided at retail counter	4	50.00	4
11. FM Channels (Radio)	4	50.00	4
12. Local TV Channels	4	50.00	4
13. Information about new arrivals is provided through company's newsletter	3	37.50	5

For informing about new product or scheme to the current or potential customer retailers have given highest importance to Advertisement in local newspapers, Information about new arrivals is provided through e-mail and Mobile (SMS). Their next priority is Pamphlets, Calls made by Call centers or customer query through Toll free help lines and Wall Ads/ Billboards/ Hoardings. E-mail response, Information provided on company's web site also chosen as means of communication but less reliance is placed on these mediums. Retailers seldom consider Product demonstration, Information at retail counter, FM Channels (Radio), Local TV Channels as important channels of information. Information about new arrivals provided through company's newsletter is the least favored option by retailers.

Table 6: Facilities/ Services available with retailers during usage of the product

Facility / Service	N	%	Rank
1. Facility to get replacement for faulty products	7	87.50	1
2. A toll free service helpline	7	87.50	1
3. Phone calls	7	87.50	1
4. Facility for receiving service request at counter	7	87.50	1
5. A website for receiving service request	6	75.00	2
6. Policy to reduce financial risk through money back guarantees or other methods that help customers gain confidence in purchase	5	62.50	3
7. An e-mail ID for sending service request	5	62.50	3

Retailers adopt several measures for ensuring the usage of the product convenient for customers. Among these facility to get replacement for faulty products, a toll free service helpline, phone calls and facility for receiving service request at counter are considered most significant by the retailers. Website for receiving service request is considered next most important service followed by policy to reduce financial risk through money back guarantees or other methods that help customers gain confidence in purchase and an e-mail ID for sending service request.

Practices for enhancing and facilitating core services**Efforts in providing training to their staff**

Training is an important factor for improving the performance of employees. Primary touch points for the customers in a retail store are the front line staff or the employees they directly interact with. Hence it is important to analyze the efforts made by the retail store in providing training to their employees.

Table 7: Response of retailers towards the policies for providing special training to working staff

Response	N	%
Yes	8	100.00
No	0	0.00
Total	8	100.00

All the retailers provide special training to the working staff of the store.

Table 8: Areas at which training is provided by retailers

Response	N	%
Product training	8	100.00
Customer Handling Behaviour	8	100.00
Handling customer problems	8	100.00
Helping customer in product selection	8	100.00
Attire / Dressing	6	75.00
How to handle phone calls	4	50.00

Product training, Customer Handling Behaviour, Handling customer problems and Helping customer in product selection are the areas where all the retailers provide training to the staff. Most of the retailers (75%) also provide training related to attire and dressing and 50% of the retailers train their staff on handling phone calls.

Standards for quick service

Table 9: Response of retailers towards setting standards for quick service

Response	N	%
Yes	8	100.00
No	0	0.00
Total	8	100.00

All the retailers have standards for 'Quick service' to the customers.

Other relationship building practices**Table 10: CRM practices adopted by retailers**

Action	N	%
Payment facility through various modes of payments e.g. Cash, debit card, credit card, cheques etc.	8	100.00
Loyalty bonus	8	100.00
Background music	7	87.50
Maintain customer Complaints book	7	87.50
Emergency support (Medical Help / Safety / Security / Fire Brigade)	7	87.50
Personal assistance in selecting merchandise?	7	87.50
Facilities for shoppers with special needs (e.g. wheel chairs for physically challenged persons)	6	75.00
Facilities provided for gift wrapping	6	75.00
Proper sitting arrangement for customers?	6	75.00
Facility of drinking water for customers	6	75.00
Proper arrangement for child care while their parents are making purchase	5	62.50
Home Delivery service	4	50.00
Entertainment for Children (Like - Playing facilities)	3	37.50

Facility of payment through cash, debit /credit card and cheque and loyalty bonus is provided by all the retailers. Except for one, all the retailers have emergency support and maintain complaint books, offer personal assistance in selecting merchandise and focus on background music. Six retailers have provisions of facilities like wheel chairs for shoppers having special needs, arrangements for seating, facility of gift wrapping and drinking water. Five retailers have proper arrangement of child care which eases the shopping experience of parents. Four retailers have home delivery services while three retailers also have entertainment facility for children.

Conclusion

CRM is an amalgamation of business processes, human resources and software. Creating the right ecosystem and proper implementation will help in reducing customer defection, gain customer trust and build loyalty. Satisfaction increases because customer insight allows companies to understand their customers better, and create improved customer value propositions and better customer experiences. As satisfaction rises, so does customer intention to repurchase and loyalty. Hence, the philosophy plays an important role for retailers in improving their business performance.

Limitation of the Study

The present work dwells on the area of customer relationship management which is pertinent in today's competitive business environment. However no research work is perfect in all respect. The present work is no exception to this common experience. Important limitations experienced by the researcher are as follows:

1. The study was limited to only cities of Udaipur, Jaipur and Ajmer. Hence the study may have not been able to reflect the diversity which is present in different regions of Rajasthan.
2. The study was limited to only goods retailing. Service retailing is not studied.
3. The present study studies the CRM practices but does not see its impact on other performance parameters.

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